

Synthesis and study of new mesogenic homologous series : 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

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Abstract : A new homologous series of liquid crystals viz. 4-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes are studied with a view to understand mesomorphic characteristics of the molecule. The nematic mesophase appeared as threaded type of texture. The first five and sixteenth homologues are nonmesomorphic. Mesomorphic property commences from the sixth member of the series as nematic type without exhibition of any smectic property. Transition temperatures are observed through hot stage polarizing microscope. Analytical data supports the structure.

Keywords : Liquid crystal, mesogens, mesomorphic, nematic, smectic, polymesomorphism.

Introduction

A number of homologous series of mesogenic azoesters with normal¹⁻³ and branched⁴⁻⁸ terminal alkyl chains have been reported. Homologous series consists of -COO- and -N=N- central linkages as well as left and right *n*-alkoxy and acetyl terminal respectively. A number of homologous series which have different molecular structures were synthesized by researchers⁹⁻¹¹. Mesomorphic properties of new homologous series of -Cl being laterally substituted at the middle phenyl ring compared with other structurally similar series¹².

Experimental

4-*n*-Alkoxy benzoic acid and corresponding 4-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chlorides were synthesized by the modified method of Dave and Vora¹³. The following procedure has been adopted in this investigation. *p*-Hydroxy benzoic acid (0.1 mol), corresponding alkyl halide (0.12 mol) and potassium hydroxide (0.25 mol) were dissolved in 100 ml methanol and reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 to 4 h. 10% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution (20 ml) was added and refluxing continued for further about two hours to hydrolyse any ester formed. The solution was cooled and acidified by 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid to precipitate the corresponding alkoxy benzoic acid. Total refluxing period was extended to 7-8 h for higher members of *n*-alkoxy benzoic acids. The alkoxy benzoic acids were crystallized from ethanol or acetic acid till constant melting points were obtained.

Synthesis of *p*-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chlorides :

p-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyl chlorides were prepared by refluxing the corresponding *p*-*n*-alkoxy benzoic acids with excess of freshly distilled thionyl chloride in water bath till evolution of hydrogen chloride gas ceased. Excess of thionyl chloride was distilled off. The acid chlorides were directly used for further reaction without purification.

*Synthesis of 3-chloro-4-hydroxyphenylazo-4''-acetylbenzene was prepared by reacting *p*-aminoacetophenone and *o*-chlorophenol by known method¹⁴ :*

Preparation of diazonium salt of *p*-amino acetophenone :

p-Amino acetophenone (0.054 mol, 7.29 g) was dissolved in a mixture of 32 ml of concentrated hydrochloric acid and 32 ml of water. The solution was cooled to 0-5 °C in ice and salt, with vigorous stirring manually. The hydrochloride which precipitated, was diazotized by addition of ice-cooled solution containing 4 g NaNO₂ (0.058 mol) in 20 ml of water. The reaction mixture was stirred vigorously and the temperature was maintained between 0-5 °C. After the completion of the diazotization, it was tested by starch iodide paper. The diazonium salt solution was filtered and used for the coupling with *o*-chlorophenol.

Coupling of diazonium salt with *o*-chlorophenol :

o-Chlorophenol (0.054 mol, 5.59 ml) was dissolved in 45 ml 10% sodium hydroxide solution contained in a 400 ml beaker was cooled to 0-5 °C in an ice bath by adding few pieces of crushed ice in the solution to maintain the temperature below 5 °C. Cold diazonium salt

solution from previous reaction was added slowly with constant stirring. When all the diazonium salt solution had been added, the resulting content was allowed to stand for half an hour with occasional stirring. The azo dye was filtered, washed thoroughly with water and naturally dried. The dye was repeatedly crystallized from glacial acetic acid till constant melting point obtained. The yield is about 69%. m.p. is 178 °C.

4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes were synthesized by usual established method¹⁵ :

3-Chloro-4-hydroxyphenylazo-4'-acetylbenzene (0.01 mole) was dissolved in dry pyridine (10 ml) and was added dropwise with constant stirring to the correspond-

The transition temperatures are recorded in Table 1 for the title homologous series which were observed through a polarizing microscope provided with heating stage. Analytical data supports the structure of the molecule.

Results and discussion

The homologous series 2-(4'-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-naphthylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes are nematogenic in nature without exhibition of smectic mesophase even in the monotropic condition. The first five and sixteenth homologues are nonmesomorphic and melt relatively at higher temperatures due to their high crystallizing tendency. The mesomorphism commences from sixth member of the se-

Table 1. Transition temperatures of the homologous series : 4-(4''-*n*-alkoxy benzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

Series-1 : 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxy benzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

Sr. no.	R = <i>n</i> -alkyl chain	Transition temp. (°C)		
		Smectic	Nematic	Isotropic
1.	Methyl	-	-	175.0
2.	Ethyl	-	-	160.0
3.	Propyl	-	-	146.0
4.	Butyl	-	-	133.0
5.	Pentyl	-	-	123.0
6.	Hexyl	-	94.0	135.0
7.	Octyl	-	98.0	125.0
8.	Decyl	-	85.0	133.0
9.	Dodecyl	-	80.0	125.0
10.	Tetradecyl	-	74.0	96.0
11.	Hexadecyl	-	-	89.0

¹H NMR : 4-(4'-*n*-Decyloxy benzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes : (200 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) : 1.111 (-CH₃ of C₁₀H₂₁), 2.668 (-COCH₃), 7.263 (-C₆H₄).

¹H NMR : 4-(4'-*n*-Tetradecyloxy benzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes : (200 MHz) δ (CDCl₃) (ppm) : 0.994 (-CH₃ of C₁₄H₂₉), 2.386 (-COCH₃), 4.041 (-O-CH₂ of C₁₄H₂₉), 6.951 and 7.262 (*p*-sub. benzenes), 8.065 and 8.101 (*p*-sub. benzenes).

ing *p*-*n*-alkoxy benzoyl chlorides (0.015 mol). The reaction mixture was warmed on water bath for about an hour and allowed to stand overnight. It was decomposed with cold 1 : 1 hydrochloric acid next day. The precipitates obtained were filtered, washed with water, 10% aqueous sodium bicarbonate solution and again with water. The solid esters were crystallized from ethanol 80% and benzene till constant melting point were obtained.

ries as nematic¹⁶. Usual odd even effect is not observed in nematic-isotropic transition curve because mesomorphism commences later and further continued for even members only. Transition temperatures of the homologues are plotted against the number of carbon atoms in *n*-alkyl chain of the left alkoxy terminals as given in Fig. 1. From the results recorded in Table 1, smooth curves are drawn through the points for like or related transitions.

Series-(1) : 4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

Fig. 1

From the phase diagram, it is seen that the solid-mesomorphic or solid-isotropic transition curve shows overall continuously falling tendency. The nematic phase appeared has threaded type of texture as judged directly by visualizing the sample of the homologues in a field of view of the hot stage polarizing microscope. The mesomorphic range varying 22 °C to a maximum of 48 °C at the tenth homologue of the series.

The present homologous Series-(1) under discussion is compared with other structurally similar homologous Series-(A) and Series-(B) for their molecular characteristics and thermal stabilities as shown in Table 2.

The present homologous Series-(1) under discussion is compared with other structurally similar homologous Series-(A)¹⁷ and Series-(B)¹² for their molecular characteristics and thermal stabilities as shown in Table 2.

The relative thermal stabilities of Series-(1), -(A) and -(B) are given in Table 2.

Series-(1)

4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-chlorophenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

Table 2. Average thermal stabilities

Series	Average thermal stabilities (°C)		
	Series-(1)	Series-(A)	Series-(B)
Smectic-nematic or smectic-isotropic	-	112.0	192.0
Commencement of nematic phase	-	(C ₁₂ -C ₁₆) C ₁₂	(C ₁₂ -C ₁₆) C ₁₂
Nematic-isotropic or isotropic-nematic	122.8 (C ₆ -C ₁₄)	124.8 (C ₆ -C ₁₆)	260.3 (C ₁ -C ₁₀)
Commencement of smectic phase	C ₆	C ₆	C ₁

Series-(A)

4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-methoxyphenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

Series-(B)

4-(4'-*n*-Alkoxybenzoyloxy)-3-phenylazo-4''-acetylbenzenes

The intermolecular forces of attractions arising out of aromaticity, planarity, length to breadth ratio, molecular polarity and polarizability etc. balancing in such a way from sixth to fourteenth homologues that only statistically parallel orientations of molecules are maintained in floating condition of resulting molten mass of sample with appearance of only nematic mesophase without display of any smectic mesophase.

The variation of mesomorphic range and degree of mesomorphism for homologue to homologue and series to series is attributed to the variation of polarity and polarizability of lateral substituents present viz. -Cl, -OCH₃ and -H which causes of variation of magnitude of lateral molecular attractions. Thus smectic mesophase commences from 12th homologue in case of Series-(A) and -(B) but it does not commence even upto the last homologue for Series-(1). Nematic-isotropic average thermal stability of homologous Series-(1) is the lowest amongst the group of Series-(1), -(A) and -(B) (Table 2). This can be attributed to the presence of chloro group at middle phenyl ring. The intermolecular distance amongst the molecule of the homologues of Series-(B) being closest increases the intermolecular forces of attractions and hence the upper transition value happens to be higher is obvious. Thus -COCH₃ functional group with -H is more efficient to bind molecules. Thus smectic and nematic group efficiency derived on the basis of thermal stability is as follows :

Smectic and nematic : -H > -OCH₃ > -Cl

Conclusions :

A new homologous series of mesogens with -COO- and -N=N- central bridges with -COCH₃ as right terminal is synthesized.

The smectic and nematic group efficiency order derived is as follows :

Smectic and nematic : -H > -OCH₃ > -Cl.

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